

THE EFFECT OF PROCESSING TIME AND TEMPERATURE ON THE INTERFACIAL REACTION OF Al/SiC COMPOSITE

Ray Y. Lin

(Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Cincinnati, M. L. #12, Cincinnati, OH 45221, USA)

ABSTRACT

The interfacial reaction between aluminum matrix and silicon carbide reinforcement in Al/SiC composites has been studied between 700 and 980°C. Examinations with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and an energy dispersive x-ray analyzer (EDAX) revealed that SiC dissolved in molten aluminum during the processing of composites. The extent of the dissolution reaction increases with the increasing time and temperature of the casting operation. Thermodynamic calculations suggest that the Si content in molten Al in the vicinity of SiC surface can be as high as 15.5 wt.% at 800°C. Kinetically, however, it is concluded that the equilibrium condition is not reached at the Al/SiC interfaces. Thus, the diffusion of Si in molten Al is not the rate determining step in the dissolution of SiC in molten aluminum. The chemical dissolution of solid SiC in molten Al appears to control the Al/SiC interaction. The rate of the SiC dissolution has been derived as a function of the processing temperature based on the experimental results of this study.

INTRODUCTION

The interfacial strength in the Metal Matrix Composite (MMC) systems depends, primarily, on the reactions occurring in the interfacial region between the matrix and the reinforcement. Adequate bonding between the matrix and the reinforcements is essential to enable maximum loading of fibers. In choosing a reinforcement for a matrix, any potential reaction between the matrix and the reinforcement must be carefully evaluated. Thus, a study of the compatibility between the matrix and the reinforcement under conditions similar to the fabrication processes or applications is a prerequisite in developing advanced engineered materials. During the fabrication of aluminum/silicon carbide composite materials, the reaction at the aluminum and silicon carbide interface depends on such fabrication parameters as temperature, atmosphere, and the chemical composition of both the aluminum matrix and the SiC reinforcement. In earlier studies^{1,2} of the Al/SiC system, the author has observed both the dissolution of SiC and the formation of third phase precipitates in the processing of composites through casting. Different types of interfacial reactions may exist, including the dissolution of SiC in Al, the third phase particle precipitation, or a complete third phase layer segregation in the interfacial region. Iseki et al. examined the interfaces between Al and various types of SiC and found that the reaction between aluminum and silicon carbide with free silicon is not as extensive as the reaction between aluminum and silicon carbide without free silicon.³ Distinct reaction zone layers were observed through a transmission electron microscope. Using an electron diffraction technique, SiC, Al₄C₃, and Al with Si layers were identified at the interface between aluminum and SiC without free Si. Meanwhile, no Al₄C₃ product was detected when free silicon was present in SiC.

Restall and co-workers⁴ prepared SiC fiber/Al composites by vacuum infiltration of molten aluminum through a silicon carbide fiber bundle. At the matrix-fiber

interface, they found a reaction zone less than 3 mm-thick, even holding the fibers for only 15 minutes in molten aluminum at 680°C. The microprobe mapping of a cross section around the fibers revealed that, in the reaction zone, both Si and Al coexisted. A specific reaction product was not proposed. Arsenault and others⁵ examined the fracture surface of Al/SiC whisker composites produced by ARCO SILAG. The samples were fractured and examined in a scanning Auger microprobe. The fresh fracture surface showed 100% Al, even in the area of the whiskers, indicating that the fracture was through the Al layers. After sputtering the sample with an ion jet, Si and C signals were obtained, but there was no indication of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ or Al₄C₃.

Observation discrepancies exist among various research groups. It is thus the objectives of the composite program in this laboratory to investigate the fundamentals of interfacial reactions in the composite systems and to develop interfacial reaction models for the composite. In a previous paper, Kannikeswaran and Lin¹ examined the characteristics of the interfaces between aluminum and silicon carbide, with an emphasis on the effect of impurity elements in a commercial Al 1100 alloy. It appears that the trace amount of silicon in the 1100 alloy slows down the interfacial reaction. Considerations based on the physical chemistry of the composite system suggest the dissolution of SiC surfaces always occurs while in contact with molten aluminum. In a later study, the investigation on the interfacial reaction between Al and SiC has been extended into much more complicated aluminum alloys, such as 2024, 6061 and 7075, as well as genetic Al-Si-Cu alloys systems. In the present study, the kinetics of the interfacial reaction in the Al/SiC composite system is developed and experimental results on the microprobe analysis are used to compare with the physico-chemical derivations of the interfacial reaction in the Al/SiC composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

To experimentally study the interfacial reaction between Al and SiC without the interference of alloying elements, 99.99% pure Al from ALCOA was cast against SiC filaments at various temperatures. Silicon carbide filaments, approximately 1mm x 1mm x 15mm in size, were cut from 12.5 mm diameter by 12.5 mm height silicon carbide buttons using a diamond wafering blade. These silicon carbide buttons, supplied by SOHIO, were sintered in nitrogen and contained less than 0.5 percent boron as the sintering aid material, less than 5.0 percent porosity, and free of elemental Si. Before casting, the filaments were held in position in a graphite mount and then packed around with chips of aluminum alloys in an alumina tube. The entire set up was enclosed in a quartz reaction chamber, which could be evacuated using a mechanical (vacuum) pump connected to it through a series of copper tubes. The chamber was maintained at 0.1 pa throughout the experiment.

The heating was provided with a Marshall furnace using an Eurotherm Model 984 temperature controller. The furnace was preheated to the desirable temperature at a location below the reaction chamber. After evacuating the system overnight, the heated furnace was raised up to a preset position to quickly heat up the specimen. With such designs, the specimen normally reaches the experimental temperature in about five minutes. The reaction was stopped by quenching the reaction chamber at the end of a preset reaction time by quickly lowering down the furnace. The composite specimen was then removed and prepared for examination with a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Cambridge Stereoscan 600), Energy Dispersive X-ray Analyzer (EDAX), and microprobe analyses on the cross sections and SiC side of the interface.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the concentration of Si as a function of the distance from the SiC surface for composite samples processed at 700 and 980°C for 1/4 and 1 hour. Figure 2 illustrates SEM photos of composite cross sections, on which the microprobe analysis was made. The two microprobe measurements for the 980°C, 1 h specimen and the 700°C, 1/4 h specimen show that the Si concentration may be independent of the location in Al matrix away from the SiC surface. For the 980°C data, the Si

Fig. 1 Experimental results on the Si concentration in Al matrix by microprobe analysis.

Fig. 2 SEM back scattering photo of the Al/SiC composite interface processed at 700°C for 1 hour under vacuum.

concentration of the 1/4 h sample is about one quarter of that of the 1 h sample. Similar relationship between the Si concentration and the processing time holds for data at 700°C. These results will be used to establish the interfacial reaction model in the followings.

1. Thermodynamics of the Al/SiC System

There is no phase diagram of the ternary Al-Si-C system available in the literature. At temperatures for the processing of composite, i.e., below 1000°C, SiC and Al₄C₃ are the only two known stable binary compounds. The mutual dissolution data of these two carbides, if any, are also not available in the literature. In this study, calculations are carried out based on stoichiometric carbides. From the JANAF Tables⁶, the Gibbs free energies of a few reactions in the Al/SiC system may

be obtained as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Gibbs free energies of reactions

Equation	Reaction	ΔG^0 (kJ/mol)
[1]	$3\text{SiC}(c) + 4\text{Al}(l) = \text{Al}_4\text{C}_3(s) + 3\text{Si}(l)$	$103.9 - 0.01648 T$
[2]	$\text{SiC}(s) = \text{Si}(l) + \text{C}(gr)$	$123.47 - 0.03757 T$
[3]	$\text{Al}_4\text{C}_3(s) = 4\text{Al}(l) + 3\text{C}(gr)$	$266.52 - 0.09623 T$

Using thermochemical data for the Al-Si binary system compiled by Hultgren et al.,⁷ it is calculated that, in equilibrium with both SiC(s) and Al₄C₃(s), the Al melt composition should contain 15.5 wt.% Si at 800°C with the Al activity being 0.78. The corresponding carbon activity with graphite as the standard state is 0.00312. In molten aluminum, it was reported that the maximum solubility of carbon (graphite) is 0.1 wt.%.⁸ Assuming Henrian solution behavior for carbon, the activity of carbon in Al(l) may be expressed as

$$a_C = 10 \text{ (wt.\% C)} \quad [4]$$

The concentration of carbon in equilibrium with SiC and Al₄C₃ in molten aluminum is, therefore, 0.000312 wt.%. This thermodynamic consideration suggests that, unless the Si content in the Al melt is 15.5 wt.% or higher, SiC will react with Al and form Al₄C₃. Kinetically, this condition may be reached when free Si is present on the SiC surfaces.

2. Kinetics

The interfacial reaction in the Al/SiC composite during processing may include: (1) the chemical reaction of SiC with molten Al, (2) the diffusion of Si away from the SiC surface into the bulk molten Al pool, (3) the formation of compounds when solubility products are exceeded, (4) upon cooling, further precipitation of compounds due to the decrease in the solubility product, and (5) the solidification of the matrix. In this study, the dissolution kinetics of SiC in Al will be examined closely assuming either (1) or (2) is the rate determining step.

A. First, it is assumed that the diffusion of Si in molten Al controls the SiC dissolution. In other words, thermodynamic equilibrium at the SiC surface is considered reached. It may occur in the following sequences. Initially, the concentrations of Si and C at the surface of SiC are equal if there is no preexisting free Si or C near the SiC surface and may be calculated from Eq. [2]. At 800°C, both Si and C would have an equilibrium concentration of 0.224 at.%, corresponding to 0.233 wt.% Si and 0.0996 wt.% C. Comparing with the equilibrium concentration of carbon in the presence of Al₄C₃, this is much higher. The dissolved carbon, therefore, would react with Al to form Al₄C₃. The dissolution of SiC and the formation of Al₄C₃ will proceed until the equilibrium condition derived above is reached. Fick's second law may be applied to describe the diffusion of Si in molten aluminum,

$$\frac{\partial[\text{Si}]}{\partial t} = D_{\text{Si}} \left(\frac{\partial^2[\text{Si}]}{\partial x^2} \right) \quad [5]$$

$$\text{and,} \quad \frac{[\text{Si}]}{[\text{Si}]^0} = 1 - \text{erf} \left[\frac{x}{2(D_{\text{Si}}t)^{0.5}} \right] \quad [6]$$

where [Si] is the concentration of Si in molten Al as a function of x, the distance from the SiC surface, and t, the processing time of the composite; [Si]⁰ is the surface concentration of i; D_{Si} is the diffusivity of Si in molten Al at the corresponding temperature, assuming 1*10⁻⁵ cm²/s; and erf is the error function. Figure 3 shows the estimated concentration distribution of Si in molten Al as a function of time. It predicts that, even after only 15 minutes of processing, the Si concentration in Al matrix can be as high as 10 wt.% at about 100 μm away from the SiC surface. Comparing with the experimental data shown in Fig. 1, this

Fig. 3 Theoretical Si concentration distribution in Al matrix.
 $t_1 = 15$ min, $t_2 = 30$ min, $t_3 = 1$ h.

reflects a significant deviation of about three orders of magnitude. The flux of Si diffusion at the SiC surface determines the rate of SiC dissolution and may be expressed as

$$J_{Si} = -D_{Si} \frac{d[Si]}{dx} = [Si]^0 (D_{Si}/\pi t)^{1/2}. \quad [7]$$

The SiC molar dissolution rate might equal the molar flux of Si at and away from the surface of SiC. This molar dissolution rate is converted to the thickness reduction of SiC assuming the density of SiC is 3.22 g/cm^3 . Figure 4 shows the calculated rate of SiC dissolution in molten Al at 800°C . The total SiC dissolution, S , may be obtained from the integration of Eq. [8] against time.

$$S = 2[Si]^0 (D_{Si} t / \pi)^{1/2}. \quad [8]$$

Figure 5 shows the total weight loss of SiC per cm^2 and the SiC thickness reduction

Fig. 4 Calculated rate of SiC dissolution in molten Al at 800°C assuming the Si diffusivity is $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$.

Fig. 5 Weight loss of SiC assuming the Si diffusivity is $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ at 800°C .

as a function of the processing time assuming the Si diffusivity in molten Al being $1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$. This figure, again, suggests that should the Si diffusion control the SiC dissolution, within 1 hour, SiC fibers of up to 0.33 mm in radius would have been completely dissolved. A condition not observed in experiments.

B. In the other mechanism with the rate of SiC dissolution being determined by the chemical reaction of SiC with molten Al, it implies that the diffusion of Si in molten Al is fast and that there is no Si concentration gradient in Al matrix. Thus, it is reasonable to anticipate that the forward reaction of Eq.[2] prevails at the SiC surface and no reverse reaction of Eq.[2] occur significantly. For the kinetics of a solid dissolving in a liquid, the first approximation would be a zero order reaction, or,

$$[\text{Si}] = k t, \quad [9]$$

where [Si] is the Si concentration in molten Al; k is the reaction rate constant at the processing temperature; and t is the processing time. Eq. [9] indicates that the concentration of Si in Al matrix increases linearly with the processing time at constant temperatures. This approximation appears to agree with the results from this study. From Fig. 1, it may be obtained that k for the reaction at 980°C is 0.0458 wt.%/min and 0.0187 wt.%/min for the reaction at 700°C . This dissolution rate may be converted to the rate of the SiC thickness reduction assuming the density of SiC(s) and Al(l) being 3.22 g/cm^3 and 2.35 g/cm^3 , respectively, and that the composite contains 20 vol % SiC fibers distributed homogeneously in molten Al matrix. The k values, thus, become $0.478 \mu\text{m/min}$ and $0.195 \mu\text{m/min}$. With these two points, the following relationship between k and T may be obtained,

$$\ln k (\mu\text{m/min}) = 2.37 - 3900/T \quad [10]$$

The activation energy for the decomposition reaction of SiC in molten Al is therefore about 32.4 kJ.

CONCLUSIONS

A physico-chemical consideration has been applied to derive the kinetics of the interfacial reaction of the Al/SiC composite from experiment results. It is concluded that the diffusion of Si in molten Al is not the rate determining step in the dissolution of SiC in molten aluminum. The chemical dissolution of solid SiC in molten Al appears to control the Al/SiC interaction. The rate of the SiC dissolution may be expressed as Eq. [10]. Since the experimental results in this study are very much limited, an extensive experimental program to determine the SiC dissolution at various temperatures and time is recommended for industrial applications.

REFERENCES

1. K. Kannikeswaran and R. Y. Lin, J. Metals, 39(9)(1987), 17
2. K. Kannikeswaran and R. Y. Lin, Proc. Adv. Struc. Mat., 1988
3. T. Iseki, T. Kameda and T. Maruyama, J. Mat. Sci., 19(1984), 1692.
4. J. E. Restall, A. Burnwood-Smith and K. F. A. Wallis, Met. Mat., 4(1970), 467.
5. R. J. Arsenault and C. P. Pande, Scrip. Met., 13(1984), 1131.
6. JANAF Thermochemical Tables, 2nd Ed., NSRDS-NBS37, U. S. DOC(1970); Suppl. to date, Dow Chem. Co., Midland, MI..
7. R. Hultgren, P. D. Desai, D. T. Hawkins, M. Gleiser and K. K. Kelley, "Selected Values of The Thermodynamic Properties of Binary Alloys," ASM, Metals Park, OH(1973), 211.
8. "Metals Handbook, Vol. 8, 8th ed.," ASM, Metals Park, OH(1973), 341.